

Exploring university dropout rates: a case study at a Peruvian university, Lima–Perú

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Abstract

University dropout constitutes a complex phenomenon that affects the quality and equity of higher education, particularly in Latin American contexts marked by socioeconomic inequalities. This study aimed to analyze university dropout at a Peruvian university, contributing to Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4: Quality Education, through an in-depth understanding of the factors influencing student retention. A basic qualitative approach was employed, using a single-case study design with embedded units of analysis, following Yin's methodological framework. The study was based on the triangulation of semi-structured interviews with dropout students, the experiences of academic tutors, and the analysis of institutional documents. The results show that dropout is a multifactorial phenomenon resulting from the convergence of economic, academic, and personal factors. In addition, a significant divergence was identified between the availability of institutional prevention strategies and their effective use by students, mediated by psychosocial barriers and institutional operational limitations. It is concluded that university dropout should be understood as a systemic process emerging from the interaction among students, tutors, and the institution, which calls for comprehensive strategies aimed at strengthening student retention and degree attainment.

Keywords: University dropout, student, academic tutor, educational institution, case study

I. INTRODUCTION

University dropout rates represent a structural challenge for higher education systems, with academic, social, economic, and institutional implications. In the global context, dropout rates vary considerably across countries. As stated in its publications, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2019) reports that nearly 20% of students do not complete their studies for various reasons. Furthermore, it maintains that in countries such as Japan and Korea, the dropout rate is less than 10%, compared to the United States, New Zealand, and Hungary, where the percentage is greater than 46%. On the other hand, publications by Eurostat (2020) state that Spain has a dropout rate of 18.3%, followed by Romania with 18.1%.

In Latin America, dropout rates have increased at the university level, according to (Behr et al., 2020). Colombia had a 31% student dropout rate in the first year, while Chile had 21%. In Venezuela, the percentage ranges between 55% and 60% in 2022. However, thanks to government policies (UNESCO, 2020), these percentages have decreased. On the other hand, Castro-Martínez

(2023) argues that Chile is the country with a dropout rate of less than 8%. While Bolivia has a rate of over 48%, highlighting the lack of information in the education system as a failure (Dávila Morán et al. 2022; Caselli Gismondi & Urrelo Huiman, 2021).

In the Peruvian context, the National Superintendency of Higher University Education (SUNEDU) reported in 2020 that the dropout rate exceeded 24%. The Ministry of Education (MINEDU) mentions that the dropout rate in accredited universities fell to 11.5% in the 2021-II period. This was due to the implementation of education programs aimed at promoting continuity in all education systems. Educational institutions urgently need to implement strategies with a view to student well-being (López, J., Valderrama, C., & Muñoz, A. 2023).

Dropout rates continue to be a persistent problem affecting both public and private universities, impacting educational quality indicators and the achievement of student retention targets (MINEDU, 2021; Castro-Martinez, 2023). From an educational/pedagogical perspective, dropout cannot be understood solely as the voluntary abandonment of studies but rather as the result of a complex process in which academic factors, personal circumstances, institutional dynamics, and pedagogical relationships converge (Ruffinatto et al., 2022).

In Spain, Portal Martínez et al. (2022) found that the most significant causes of dropout include financial difficulties that limit the ability to finance study expenses. Added to this is the choice of degree program, which does not always respond to a genuine vocation but is often influenced by circumstances such as proximity to home, low entrance exam scores, or family advice.

Similarly, Núñez-Naranjo, A. F. (2024) states that dropout is associated with personal, family, economic, academic, and institutional factors, contributing to abandonment with an estimated probability of 44.90%. A higher dropout rate was observed among male students in their first academic cycle. Garrido Silva, C. A., & Pajuelo Diaz, J. (2023) also maintain that the most influential factors are personal, academic, economic, and institutional. Furthermore, it was concluded that university dropout is a highly complex problem that encompasses a wide range of factors that influence students' academic lives in different ways.

From an institutional standpoint, Montalvo Márquez, F. J., & Sánchez Pozo, N. N. (2023) emphasize the importance of implementing targeted support and prevention measures, particularly for students from households with lower educational attainment and greater family responsibilities. Such evidence enables university authorities to design preventive strategies aimed at improving student retention and academic success.

However, Olvera-Guevara et al. (2023) refer to the importance of the academic tutor, highlighting the importance of their role and encouraging teachers to revisit effective aspects of study and develop a tutorial action plan as a substantive task. The tutoring system seeks to ensure that

teachers perform their role as mentors to students, providing support and guidance for their academic and personal development.

In addition, support is recognized. In this regard, Díaz-Camargot et al. (2020) highlight the monitoring and support provided to students when personal and/or cognitive problems are evident. The tutor, as a mediator, refers students to the appropriate area, noting that a high percentage of dropouts do not make use of the psychological services provided by the university welfare department. The economic dimension was not found to be significantly related to retention.

In this sense, the study allows us to understand the phenomenon from the perspective of the actors involved, providing interpretive consistency to the factors presented. It is necessary to understand and identify the existing problem through an in-depth analysis that guides us in making a diagnosis of the reality, and based on this, propose new approaches, expectations, and improvements that are effective in reducing the figures and increasing student retention (Castro-Martínez, 2023; Heffington et al., 2024). The research is based on the methodological approach of Robert Yin, who argues that case studies are relevant when “how” and “why” questions are asked, and especially when there is limited control over the events studied (Yin, 2018). Given this context, the general question is, how and why does the phenomenon of university dropout manifest itself in the context of a Peruvian university in Lima?

Theoretical framework

University dropout has been addressed from various theoretical perspectives, recognizing its multifactorial nature. Previous research highlights the influence of economic factors, such as the inability to cover educational costs, the need for early entry into the labor market, and unforeseen family crises (Portal Martínez et al., 2022). These factors often interact with academic variables, such as poor performance, failing grades, and personal factors such as difficulty adapting to the pace of university life (Barrantes-Morales et al., 2021).

From an institutional perspective, the importance of prevention policies, mentoring programs, early warning systems, and student welfare services is recognized as key strategies for retention (Sansores et al., 2023). However, several studies indicate that the existence of these programs does not guarantee their effectiveness if they are not properly aligned with the real needs of students (Barragán Moreno & González Támara, 2017).

The role of the tutor teacher is important as a pedagogical mediator and agent for early detection of the risk of dropout. University tutoring, understood as comprehensive support, goes beyond academic support and focuses on personal, emotional, and social dimensions (Rabuco Hidalgo, 2022). Likewise, the literature emphasizes the importance of support in socio-emotional skills

and the institutional climate in the student experience, where the support of the academic tutor is crucial (Olvera-Guevara et al., 2023).

From a methodological perspective, Yin argues that case studies allow contemporary phenomena to be analyzed within their real context, using multiple sources of evidence and favoring triangulation as a validation strategy. This approach is particularly relevant for the analysis of university dropout rates.

II METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted using a qualitative, descriptive, and analytical approach, with the basic aim of expanding knowledge about the phenomenon of university dropout. The single case study method with embedded units of analysis was used, following Robert Yin's approach.

The case study consisted of a private university located in Lima, Peru, for which three units of analysis were taken: educational institution, teaching tutor, and dropout student. This design allowed for a multilevel analysis of the phenomenon, integrating institutional, pedagogical, and experiential perspectives.

The sample was selected through purposive sampling. The participants were 10 dropout students, 8 teachers with academic tutoring responsibilities, and 2 school coordinators involved in pedagogical management, including student retention. The number of participants responded to theoretical saturation criteria (Arias Gonzáles, 2021), as there are no specific parameters regarding the number of samples as a reference in these types of case studies (Hernández-Sampieri, 2018). Semi-structured interviews were used as the data collection instrument for each unit of analysis, along with document analysis sheets for reviewing institutional regulations, policies, and programs, as well as a field diary. The instruments were validated by expert judgment. For the procedure and analysis of the collected data, these were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis, supported by ATLAS.ti statistical software, through a systematic process of coding and categorization. Subsequently, the data were interpreted and analyzed through methodological triangulation.

III RESULTS

From a general perspective, the findings show that university dropout rates are not due to a single factor but rather to a convergence of economic, academic, personal, and institutional causes. Students who drop out describe trajectories marked by financial pressures when unexpected events affect the family economy, poor academic performance in difficult courses or with very demanding teachers, and the students' own personal problems, such as difficulties in emotional adaptation, the involvement of tutors, and the application of institutional policies.

A. Study category: University dropout

The phenomenon of university dropout in the context of a Peruvian university in Lima-Peru.

Source: Processed in ATLAS. Ti 25

Fig. 1 shows a hierarchical categorical map that articulates the explanatory elements of the phenomenon under study, organizing them into four analytical subcategories. Each of the subcategories contains nodes that arise from a qualitative analysis of an institutional case, and their arrangement makes it possible to understand dropout as a multidimensional phenomenon in which personal, structural, institutional, and experiential factors converge. This result reinforces the idea that dropout should not be understood as an individual decision, but rather as a systemic process in which the student-teacher-institution experience is a determining factor.

B. Subcategory 1

Key factors contributing to dropout rates, as revealed by the narratives of students who have dropped out, and how these factors are intertwined with their individual life cycles.

Triangulation of dropout factors

Source: Processed in ATLAS. Ti 25

Fig. 2 shows the triangulation of dropout factors, data from the narratives of dropout students and the factors present in them. The findings demonstrate a series of factors that often force students to drop out if they are not addressed in a timely manner. Analysis of the study units allowed us to identify significant convergences and divergences between them, which are often not addressed or simply not identified. There is consensus that economic factors act as initial triggers, which are exacerbated when combined with academic demands and limited emotional support.

With regard to institutional prevention strategies and policies, the institution has a regulatory framework, regulations, and programs aimed at preventing dropouts, such as academic tutoring, mentoring, financial support, and psycho-pedagogical services. However, a discrepancy was identified between the design of these strategies and their effective implementation, where the strategies do not necessarily reach students for simple reasons such as the means of communication used to reach them, which are often ignored by students.

The role and functions of tutors: this unit of analysis plays a key role as agents for the early detection of the risk of dropout. Their work is based on observing absenteeism, changes in attitude, and poor academic performance. However, teachers point out limitations related to workload and insufficient institutional resources. Their comprehensive involvement with students makes them mediators, with the ability to refer specific areas for timely attention.

Dropout students recognize the existence of institutional resources, either through their own efforts or through guidance from their teachers or classmates, but their use is limited by emotional barriers, mainly the embarrassment of admitting academic difficulties. They are invited to tutoring sessions but do not always attend, nor do they always seek psycho-emotional support from professionals. There is a preference for virtual and asynchronous resources, which offer anonymity and flexibility.

The three units of analysis: educational institution, teacher-tutor, and dropout student, reveal certain difficulties at the time of the interview, but upon reviewing institutional documents, a solid prevention policy is evident, considering different aspects related to the issue of dropout among university students. Academic support is provided in person by teacher-tutors from different subjects. In addition, teachers receive ongoing training, and academic material is available to all students on the educational platform 24 hours a day. These programs are updated each academic semester and contain videos, tutorials, and assessments. However, students often do not use them, either due to a lack of information or a lack of commitment to themselves. It is true that there are deficiencies in each unit of analysis. The task is to continue improving, meet needs, and listen to the protagonists of this study. The road is long, and we must keep moving forward.

C. Integration of the categories

Triangulation of Prevention Strategies

Source: Processed in ATLAS. Ti 25

Fig. 3 shows the triangulation on the implementation and effectiveness of prevention strategies (subcategories 2, 3, and 4). This is the most critical point of triangulation, as it compares what the institution has as “policies and strategies” with what teachers do based on their “experience” as well as how students “perceive the effectiveness” of the programs. Divergences occur when the different units of study do not show evidence and/or are not aligned, or when one of the units limits or contradicts the findings of another unit on the same phenomenon. For example, among teachers, the divergence between design and execution shows that the intervention works, but its overall effectiveness is frustrated by failures in institutional communication and a lack of psycho-

emotional support. With regard to students, there is a divergence between availability and utilization. The availability of resources is negated by internal psychosocial barriers (embarrassment about accepting academic weakness). On the other hand, the lack of effective dissemination and ignorance about the different virtual/asynchronous tools available on the platform suggest a search for anonymity and flexibility.

IV DISCUSSION

This qualitative case study analyzed university dropout as a complex and contextualized phenomenon by triangulating narratives from dropout students, faculty advisors, and institutional documents, in line with Yin's (1994) methodological approach. This strategy strengthened the study's validity and allowed for an understanding of the phenomenon from multiple levels of analysis.

The results confirm the multifactorial nature of dropout, determined by the interaction of economic, academic, personal, and social factors, in agreement with Bonilla-Jurado et al. (2023) and De la Cruz-Campos et al. (2023). Economic difficulties, associated with family crises and the need to work, emerge as a structural factor that directly impacts academic performance and time management, coinciding with Portal Martínez et al. (2022) and Liza and García-Salirrosas (2022). Likewise, poor performance and failure in critical courses constitute academic turning points, reinforcing the findings of Cabezas and Escobar (2022) regarding the need for early warning systems.

In the personal and vocational sphere, the findings show that professional disorientation, emotional distress, and difficulties with social integration significantly influence the decision to drop out, in line with López et al. (2023) and Delgado-Villalobos et al. (2021). A relevant contribution of the study is the identification of shame and fear of stigma as internal psychosocial barriers that limit the use of support services, even when these are known, expanding on the findings of Dávila Morán et al. (2022).

From an institutional perspective, a solid regulatory framework aimed at preventing dropouts was identified, with comprehensive academic, financial, and psycho-pedagogical support strategies, consistent with Barragán Moreno and González Támara (2020) and Sansores et al. (2023). However, the research reveals a critical divergence between the design of these policies and their effective implementation, attributed mainly to deficiencies in institutional communication and limited operational coordination, an aspect that coincides with Núñez-Naranjo (2024).

Regarding the role of the academic tutor, the results highlight their key function as an agent of early detection and institutional mediator, in agreement with Cabezas and Escobar (2022). However, the study provides empirical evidence showing that the effectiveness of tutorial support

depends on organizational support, the availability of psycho-emotional resources, and formal recognition of this work, in line with González and Centella-Centeno (2022).

Finally, from the perspective of dropout students, there is a significant gap between the availability and use of institutional resources, explained by emotional barriers and a preference for asynchronous and virtual self-learning tools, which offer flexibility and reduce stigma, in line with Jaimes-Medrano et al. (2024). Likewise, financial incentives are recognized as a key factor for retention, reinforcing the findings of Otero Escobar (2021).

From a methodological perspective, the application of the case study with embedded units allowed for the integration of multiple sources of evidence, strengthening the internal validity of the study through triangulation. In terms of scientific contribution, this research contributes to the educational literature by offering a contextualized understanding of university dropout rates at a Peruvian university, highlighting the need to articulate institutional policies, teaching practices, and students' socio-emotional dimensions in order to design more effective prevention strategies.

V CONCLUSIONS

University dropout is a multifactorial and dynamic phenomenon that affects educational quality and constitutes a complex socio-educational problem. Its origin is due to the convergence of internal factors, linked to psychological and vocational aspects of the student, and external factors of an economic, social, and institutional nature, which interact and condition the decision to drop out.

From the perspective of students who drop out, dropping out is not due to a single cause, but rather to an accumulation of economic, academic, social, and personal difficulties. Financial crises and the need to work have a negative impact on time management and academic performance, a situation that is exacerbated by perceptions of high teaching demands, vocational disorientation, and emotional distress, although in some cases dropping out is seen as a strategic decision to reorient one's education.

At the institutional level, the university has a regulatory framework and a comprehensive system for preventing dropouts that includes academic, financial, and psycho-pedagogical support, as well as early warning mechanisms. However, there is a gap between the design of these policies and their effective implementation, mainly due to limitations in the psycho-emotional resources available and deficiencies in institutional communication channels.

The academic advisor plays a key role as an early detection agent and institutional mediator, with a positive impact on supporting at-risk students. However, the effectiveness of the system is conditioned by students' internal psychosocial barriers, such as stigma and shame in seeking help, which limits the use of available services. In this context, students show a preference for virtual

and asynchronous strategies, while financial incentives and active teacher support are consolidating as relevant factors for university retention.

The study provides evidence for the design of educational policies aimed at student retention, highlighting the importance of comprehensive support, effective communication, and attention to socio-emotional dimensions.

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